

1 **Plasma metabolomic signature of combined healthy lifestyle, structural brain**
2 **reserve, and risk of dementia**

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24 **ABSTRACT:**

25 Although the association between healthy lifestyle and dementia risk has been
26 documented, the relationship between a metabolic signature indicative of healthy
27 lifestyle and dementia risk as well as the mediating role of structural brain
28 impairment, remains unknown.

29 We retrieved 136,628 dementia-free participants from UK Biobank. Elastic net
30 regression was employed to obtain a metabolic signature that represented lifestyle
31 behaviors. Cox proportional hazard models were fitted to explore the associations of
32 lifestyle-associated metabolic signature with incident dementia. Causal associations
33 between identified metabolites and dementia were investigated using Mendelian
34 randomization (MR). Mediation analysis was further conducted to uncover the
35 potential mechanisms involving 19 imaging-derived phenotypes (brain volume, gray
36 matter volume, white matter volume, and regional gray matter volumes).

37 During a follow-up of 12.55 years, 1,783 incident cases of all-cause dementia (ACD)
38 were identified, including 725 cases of Alzheimer's dementia (AD) and 418 cases of
39 vascular dementia (VaD). We identified 83 metabolites that could represent healthy
40 lifestyle behaviors using elastic net regression. The metabolic signature was
41 associated with a lower dementia risk, and for each standard deviation increment in
42 metabolic signature, the hazard ratio (HR) was 0.89 (95% confidence interval [CI]:
43 0.85, 0.93) for ACD, 0.95 (95% CI: 0.88, 1.03) for AD, and 0.84 (95% CI: 0.77, 0.91)
44 for VaD. MR revealed potential causal associations between the identified metabolites
45 and risk of dementia. In addition, the specific structural brain reserve, including the
46 hippocampus, gray matter in the hippocampus, parahippocampal gyrus, and middle
47 temporal gyrus, were detected to mediate the effects of metabolic signature on
48 dementia risk (mediated proportion ranging from 6.21% to 11.98%).

49 The metabolic signature associated with a healthy lifestyle is inversely associated with
50 dementia risk and greater structural brain reserve play an important role in mediating
51 this relationship. These findings hold significant implications for understanding the
52 intricate connections between lifestyle, metabolism, and brain health.

53 **Running title:** Healthy lifestyle related metabolic signature and dementia

54

55 **Keywords:** Healthy lifestyle; Metabolic signature Dementia; Brain structure; Cohort
56 study;

57 **Abbreviations:** ACD = all-cause dementia; AD = Alzheimer's dementia; VaD =
58 vascular dementia; MR = Mendelian randomization; HR= hazard ratio; CI =
59 confidence interval; NMR = nuclear magnetic resonance; MRI = magnetic resonance
60 imaging; WM = white matter; GM = grey matter; IDP = imaging-derived phenotypes;
61 ICD = International Classification of Diseases; TDI = Townsend deprivation index,
62 BMI = body mass index; *APOE* = apolipoprotein E; GWAS = genome-wide
63 association study IVW = Inverse variance-weighted SNPs = single nucleotide
64 polymorphisms C = cholesterol; CE = cholesteryl ester; FC = free cholesterol; M =
65 medium; PL = phospholipid; TG = triglyceride; S = small; L = large; VLDL = very
66 LDL; XL = very large; XS = very small; XXL = especially large.

67

68

69 **Introduction**

70 Dementia has been a paramount public health concern globally. The prevalence of
71 dementia is projected to exponentially increase in the coming three decades, driven
72 predominantly by the increasing age of the global population in combination with
73 nutritional imbalance and social stress ¹. However, effective avenues for treatment of
74 dementia remain elusive. Mounting epidemiological evidence demonstrates that
75 adherence to multifactorial healthy behaviors is associated with a reduced risk of
76 dementia. This includes refraining from smoking, engaging in only moderate alcohol
77 consumption within permissible parameters, and following a healthy diet with regular
78 exercise ²⁻⁴. In addition, some emerging lifestyle factors including adequate sleep
79 duration, non-sedentary behavior, and social intercourse have been identified to lower
80 the dementia risk, alone or in conjunction with other lifestyle factors ⁵⁻⁷. Compared
81 with individual lifestyle, combinations of these behaviors could reflect their true daily
82 performance and interact synergistically ^{8,9}. However, there are limitations in
83 accurately evaluating the effects of lifestyle behaviors, since the information
84 collection in several studies is based on subjective self-reported data fraught with
85 measurement and recall bias. In addition, it is plausible that the internal metabolic
86 response to the same healthy behaviors - such as dietary choices – shows considerable
87 variation owing to biological heterogeneity ¹⁰.

88
89 High-throughput metabolomic profiling has displayed significant potential to provide
90 objective metrics for assessing the metabolic responses of individuals to genetic and
91 lifestyle influences ¹¹. Metabolomic profiles could serve as objective indicators of
92 individual's complex lifestyle patterns ^{12, 13}, allowing rapid quantification of a
93 multitude of essential biomarkers and enabling the prompt detection of alterations in
94 the relevant biological pathways. Prior studies have identified specific metabolic
95 signatures for lifestyle behaviors, and widely explore the associations with
96 cardiovascular outcomes, including myocardial infarction, stroke, and coronary artery
97 disease ^{14, 15}, but few studies have investigated the association of metabolic signature

98 in response to healthy lifestyle and incident dementia.

99

100 Furthermore, previous studies have demonstrated that the lifestyle choices could exert
101 an influence on brain structure ¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Individuals with healthier metabolic profiles in
102 response to healthier lifestyle, characterized by balanced glucose regulation, lower
103 levels of inflammation, and better lipid metabolism, have been shown to exhibit
104 preserved brain volume and cognitive function ¹⁹. The pathological changes of brain
105 structure have also been related to a higher risk of dementia ^{20,21}. However, it remains
106 unclear whether these changes in the brain structure alter or play a role in mediating
107 the relationship between metabolic signature indicative of a healthy lifestyle and
108 dementia. This warrants further investigation.

109

110 In this study, we identified and validated the metabolic signature in response to
111 adherence to a healthy lifestyle, and examined the relationship between of the
112 lifestyle-associated metabolic signature and incident dementia using available nuclear
113 magnetic resonance (NMR) metabolomics data from UK biobank study.

114 Subsequently, the causal relationships were studied using Mendelian randomization.

115 We further evaluated the possible mechanisms and mediating roles of brain structures
116 underlying these associations.

117

118 **Methods**

119 **Study participants and metabolite profiling**

120 The UK Biobank is a prospective cohort study comprising approximately 500,000
121 participants aged 40 to 69 years who were recruited between 2006 and 2010. These
122 participants came from various locations across England, Scotland, and Wales, where
123 they underwent initial assessments at 22 different centers. Detailed description of the
124 study has been previously published ²². Our study enrolled dementia-free participants
125 and excluded those with prevalent cancer. In addition, participants without data on
126 lifestyle assessment and NMR metabolomics were excluded from the study, leaving

127 136,628 in the final analyses (**Figure S1**). This study received approval from the
128 North West-Haydock Research Ethics Committee (NO.16/NW/0274).
129
130 Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) metabolomic profiling data was obtained from
131 Nightingale Health. Currently, data is accessible for Phase 1 and Phase 2 of the study.
132 These phases involved measuring 251 metabolic biomarkers (170 metabolites
133 measured in absolute level and 81 composite ratio indexes) for EDTA plasma samples
134 collected from around 280,000 participants in the UK Biobank. A high-throughput
135 NMR-based metabolic biomarker profiling platform was utilized for this purpose.
136 Additionally, approximately 16,000 participants completed the initial repeat
137 assessment visit. Detailed information pertaining to the profiling process and quality
138 control have been published online.²³ The biomarkers include a wide range of
139 metabolic pathways, including low-molecular weight metabolites (amino acids,
140 ketone bodies, and glycolysis metabolites), lipoprotein lipids (14 subclasses), fatty
141 acids, and fatty acid compositions.

142

143 **Assessment of healthy lifestyle score**

144 To construct a composite healthy lifestyle score, we chose seven modifiable factors
145 guided by prior evidence⁵⁻⁹. These factors encompass four conventional elements:
146 smoking status, alcohol consumption, diet quality, and physical activity, along with
147 three emerging factors: sleep duration, sedentary behavior, and social contact. A score
148 of 1 point was allocated for each healthy behavior, and the overall lifestyle score was
149 derived as the cumulative sum of these factors, ranging from 0 to 7. The data for these
150 factors were gathered during the baseline assessment using a touchscreen
151 questionnaire, with comprehensive definitions and measurement methods outlined in
152 **Table S1**. In particular, health-promoting behaviors were defined as follows:
153 abstaining from current smoking, maintaining alcohol consumption levels below < 6
154 standard drinks per week for women or < 8 standard drinks per week for men²⁴,
155 regular participation in physical activity (achieving 150 minutes of moderate intensity

156 activity weekly or 75 minutes of vigorous activity weekly), adherence to at least two
157 of the healthy food items (increased consumption of fruits, vegetables, fish, and whole
158 grains, and reduced intake of red meat, processed products, and refined grains),
159 obtaining 7 to 9 hours of daily sleep duration ²⁵, limiting sedentary behavior to less
160 than 4 hours per day, and increasing engagement in social activities.

161

162 **Brain imaging structure**

163 This ongoing cohort provided the brain structure data extracted from magnetic
164 resonance imaging (MRI) by using 3-Tesla Siemens Skyra scanners since 2014 ²⁶. We
165 used total brain, total white matter (WM), total hippocampus, total grey matter (GM),
166 total GM in hippocampus, GM in the superior frontal gyrus, GM in the middle frontal
167 gyrus, GM in the inferior frontal gyrus, GM in frontal pole, GM in the precentral
168 gyrus, GM in the precuneus, GM in the postcentral gyrus, GM in the inferior temporal
169 gyrus, GM in the parahippocampal gyrus, GM in the middle temporal gyrus, caudate,
170 thalamus, putamen, and amygdala volumes (in mm³) as imaging of interest. These
171 imaging-derived phenotypes (IDP) were obtained by a UK Biobank image-processing
172 pipeline ²⁷. Total brain, GM, and WM volumes were normalized for head size, and
173 other IDPs were calculated by mean of right and left structural volumes. These
174 imaging outcomes were then standardized.

175

176 **Follow-up and ascertainment of dementia**

177 Follow-up assessments were performed for each participant after the initial
178 recruitment until the date of first diagnosis of dementia, date of mortality, date of
179 attrition from the follow-up, or the end of follow-up date (September 30, 2021 for
180 England, July 31, 2021 for Scotland, and February 28, 2018 for Wales), whichever
181 occurred first. The outcomes of all-cause dementia, Alzheimer's dementia, and
182 vascular dementia were ascertained by the linkage of hospital inpatient records
183 obtained from Health Episode Statistics in England and Wales, along with the Scottish
184 Morbidity Records in Scotland. UK biobank provided the algorithms to identify

185 incident dementia, which combined the comprehensive information from multiple
186 data sources²⁸. International Classification of Diseases (ICD) coding system was used
187 to document the diagnosis of dementia, with detailed listings of the ICD-9 and ICD-
188 10 codes provided in **Table S2**.

189

190 **Assessment of covariates**

191 Sociodemographic factors and medical history associated with dementia risk were
192 considered as potential confounders, which were assessed through questionnaires.
193 Covariates included age at baseline, sex (male and female), race (white and non-
194 white), education level (college education or less than college education), Townsend
195 deprivation index (TDI), body mass index (BMI), family history of dementia,
196 apolipoprotein E (*APOE*) ϵ 4 carrier status, prevalent status of hypertension, diabetes,
197 and depression. TDI examines the material well-being of individuals and households
198 based on factors such as income, employment, and access to services. The index
199 scores were from 0 to 1, with a higher score indicating greater deprivation. Data on
200 prevalent hypertension, diabetes and depression were acquired through a combination
201 of self-reported information and inpatient records. *APOE* haplotypes were evaluated
202 using genetic data and stratified into two distinct groups: *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers, which
203 encompassed individuals possessing any ϵ 4 allele, and noncarriers.

204

205 **Statistical analysis**

206 **Identifying the metabolic signature reflecting healthy lifestyle**

207 We identified metabolites to reflect adherence to healthy lifestyle for dementia, and
208 considered the baseline metabolomics data of UK biobank as training set. Prior to
209 undertaking planned analyses, all 251 metabolites were log transformed and
210 standardized to the same scale, and correlations between them were examined through
211 Pearson correlation coefficient. The associations of each metabolite with lifestyle and
212 its components were explored using multivariable linear regression, and $P <$
213 Bonferroni corrected 0.05 was considered as statistically significant. At the first step,

214 elastic net regression model was performed to screen metabolites and reflect
215 metabolic signature for healthy lifestyle (**Figure 1A**). This preferred approach is a
216 classification algorithm that combines the advantages of lasso and ridge methods,
217 which could handle multicollinearity, reduce overfitting, and select relevant features
218 ²⁹. We regressed healthy lifestyle score on 251 named and standardized metabolites
219 and selected the optimal lambda parameter through a 10-fold cross-validation
220 approach, where the chosen lambda yielded a mean squared error within one standard
221 error of the minimum. Further, we calculated the total metabolic signature by taking
222 the weighted sum of the chosen metabolites (coefficients $\neq 0$), with each weight
223 corresponding to the coefficients obtained from the elastic net regression. The total
224 metabolic signature represented the combined effects of the weighted sum of the
225 selected metabolites.

226

227 **Associations between healthy lifestyle, metabolic signature, and dementia**

228 At the second step, Cox proportional hazard models were conducted to obtain hazard
229 ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) associated with of the associations of
230 healthy lifestyle score and metabolomic signature with dementia risk. Three models
231 were developed through sequentially including three sets of covariates to account for
232 potential confounders. The basic model only adjusted age and sex. Model 2 expanded
233 to include ethnicity, TDI, education level BMI, family history, *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carrier's
234 status and prevalent status of hypertension, diabetes, and depression. In Model 3, we
235 further included mutual adjustment for both lifestyle score and the metabolic signature
236 simultaneously to assess their independent associations. Importantly, we performed an
237 internal validation using the confirmatory data set. No violations of the proportional
238 hazard assumptions were detected through the significance testing of Schoenfeld
239 residuals. We further examined the potential nonlinear association between metabolic
240 signature, lifestyle score and dementia risk using restricted cubic spline analysis.
241 Meanwhile, Kaplan-Meier survival curves were mapped to estimate the dementia risk
242 between unfavorable and favorable metabolic signature groups.

243

244 **Subgroup analysis and sensitivity analysis**

245 The multivariable Cox models stratified by age, sex, and *APOE* ϵ 4 carrier's status
246 were also performed. Several sensitivity analyses were further conducted to examine
247 the robustness of these findings, including 1) exclusion of the participants who
248 developed incident dementia within three years of follow-up duration; 2) exclusion of
249 the individuals aged < 60 y as dementia usually occurred in the older; 3) additional
250 adjustment for diabetes medication, antihypertensive medication, lipid-lowering
251 medication, and use of aspirin; and 4) imputation of the missing data through chained
252 equations.

253

254 **Mediation analysis**

255 To boost explaining the associations of metabolic signature with risk of dementia, we
256 investigated the potential mediating role of brain structural mechanisms in the
257 subsequent steps. We initiated our study through Cox models to select a series of brain
258 structure phenotypes including GM, WM, total hippocampus, GM in specific brain
259 region, putamen, thalamus, caudate, and amygdala. Prior to their incorporation into
260 the analytical models, the original data underwent z-score transformation. To
261 investigate whether these brain structure phenotypes could elucidate the longitudinal
262 relationship between metabolic signature and the risk of dementia, we employed
263 bootstrapped mediation models via the "mediation" R package. Notably, mediation
264 models adjusted for confounding variables as aforementioned Model 3. Additionally,
265 the mediation effects of brain structure on the associations of each selected metabolite
266 with dementia risk were also examined to find the specific mediators and pathways.

267

268 **Mendelian randomization analyses**

269 Two-sample Mendelian randomization (MR) analyses were performed to explore the
270 potential causal associations between the identified metabolites and risk of dementia.
271 We obtained the genetic variants that were considered as instrumental variables for

272 MR from published genome-wide association study (GWAS) summary statistics for
273 each identified metabolite, which involved 115,078 participants from the UK
274 Biobank. Summary statistics for all-cause dementia were derived from three open
275 GWAS projects involving 5,933 cases and 212,859 controls, 7,284 cases and 209,487
276 controls, and 7,395 cases and 211,397 controls, respectively. Summary statistics for
277 Alzheimer's dementia were obtained from three open GWAS projects involving
278 25,580 cases and 48,466 controls [International Genomics of Alzheimer's Project
279 (IGAP) consortium], 954 cases and 487,331 controls, and 39,106 cases and 46,828
280 controls, respectively. We obtained summary statistics for vascular dementia from two
281 open GWAS projects involving 881 cases and 211,508 controls, and 859 cases and
282 211,300 controls, respectively. We conducted stringent LD clumping thresholds
283 (10,000 kb clumping window and r^2 threshold = 0.1) to select independent single
284 nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). Inverse variance-weighted (IVW) approach was
285 applied as the primary Mendelian randomization analyses to obtain the overall
286 estimates. Meta-analysis was used to obtain the combined result from multiple open
287 projects, and Cochran Q statistic and the I^2 statistic were computed to examine the
288 heterogeneity. As part of sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of our IVW
289 estimate, we also explored alternative methods, including the weighted median, MR-
290 Egger regression, and simple and weighted mode-based estimators.

291

292 Two-sided $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Bonferroni corrections
293 were applied in the analysis to account for potential errors from multiple testing. The
294 primary R packages employed in the analysis included 'glmnet' for elastic net
295 regression and 'survival' for Cox regression.

296

297 **Results**

298 **Characteristics of the participants**

299 **Table 1** shows the characteristics of study participants at baseline stratified by
300 incident dementia. A total of 136,628 individuals without a prior diagnosis of

301 dementia were enrolled in the analysis with an average (SD) age of 56.14 (8.09), of
302 which 68,527 (50.16%) were female. During a median follow-up time of 12.55 years,
303 1,783 all-cause dementia cases were identified, including 725 AD cases and 418 VaD
304 cases. Participants with incident dementia were more likely to be older, male, white,
305 with higher BMI, had less education, and were *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers. In addition, they
306 tended to have family history of dementia, and prevalent hypertension and depression
307 at the time of being diagnosed with dementia. Compared to individuals without
308 incident dementia, those with incident dementia were less likely to refrain from
309 current smoking, consume alcohol moderately, and have regular exercise, adequate
310 sleep, and frequent social contact, but were more likely to have sedentary behavior
311 (all $P < 0.05$). Moreover, it was observed that the metabolic signature scores were
312 higher in the dementia groups (**Figure S2**). Furthermore, we found that the
313 participants' characteristics at baseline were similar to those observed in the first
314 repeat data (**Table S3**).

315

316 **Identification of the healthy lifestyle-related metabolic signature**

317 This study analyzed 251 metabolites, and most of metabolites were identified to be
318 significantly associated with healthy lifestyle score at baseline (**Figure S3**), such as
319 lipoprotein lipids and fatty acids. The findings from first repeat assessment data
320 showed a high degree of concurrence (**Figure S4**). Additionally, we examined the
321 correlation among the metabolites, and observed that strong correlations and
322 clustering pattern among lipids and lipoprotein lipid subclasses (**Figure S5**).

323 Subsequently, the elastic net regressions on 251 metabolites in baseline data were
324 performed to determine the metabolic signature for healthy lifestyle. A total of 83
325 metabolites were selected from the model to calculate the total metabolic signature,
326 which was significantly correlated with healthy lifestyle score (baseline data: $r = 0.24$,
327 $P < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$; repeat assessment: $r = 0.19$, $P < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$, **Figure 1B and 1C**). These
328 metabolites in the signature included lipids, lipoprotein subclass, triglycerides,
329 glucose-lactate, fatty acids, amino acids, ketone bodies, glycolysis-related, fluid

330 balance-related, and inflammation-related metabolites (**Figure S6**). We observed the
331 extensive and consistent associations of the selected metabolites with healthy lifestyle
332 score and its components (**Figure 2**). In addition, the largest contribution to the
333 positive coefficient of the metabolic signature was primarily attributed to the linoleic
334 acid to total fatty acids percentage, the omega-3 fatty acids to total fatty acids
335 percentage, and cholesteryl esters in extremely large VLDL and chylomicrons.
336 Conversely, free cholesterol in extremely large VLDL and chylomicrons, and the
337 polyunsaturated fatty acids to total fatty acids percentage played a significant role in
338 influencing the reverse coefficient of the metabolic signature.

339

340 **Associations between dementia and healthy lifestyle score and metabolic** 341 **signature**

342 We observed that healthy lifestyle score was associated with a decreased dementia
343 risk and the associations behaved in a dose-response manner (**Table 2 and Figure**
344 **S7**). In model 3, each 1-point increase in healthy lifestyle score was associated with
345 HRs of 0.87 (95% CI: 0.84, 0.91), 0.96 (95% CI: 0.90, 1.03), and 0.82 (95% CI: 0.75,
346 0.89) for all-cause dementia, Alzheimer's dementia, and vascular dementia,
347 respectively. Specifically, inverse associations of refraining from smoking, moderate
348 alcohol consumption, healthy diet, regular physical activity, adequate sleep duration,
349 less sedentary behavior, and frequent social contact with dementia risk were also
350 documented (**Table S4**).

351

352 In multivariable-adjusted analyses, both the baseline metabolic signature and the
353 metabolic signature from the first repeat assessment were associated with a reduced
354 dementia risk [HR = 0.87 (95% CI: 0.83, 0.91) for baseline signature; 0.69 (95% CI:
355 0.53, 0.89) for first repeat data]. Notably, these associations remained statistically
356 significant even after additional adjustment for lifestyle score, with HRs of 0.88 (95%
357 CI: 0.84, 0.92) for the baseline signature and 0.70 (95% CI: 0.54, 0.91) for the first
358 repeat data. Furthermore, the baseline metabolic signature demonstrated similar

359 effects on Alzheimer's dementia and vascular dementia, with HRs of 0.95 (95% CI:
360 0.88, 1.03) and 0.84 (95% CI: 0.77, 0.91), respectively. However, in the validation
361 dataset, these associations did not reach statistical significance. The dose-response
362 curves depicted a decreased trend of dementia risk with increment of the metabolic
363 signature (**Figure S8**). In addition, log-rank test indicated a significant difference
364 among the individuals with unfavorable and favorable metabolic signature in the
365 probability of dementia at any time point in Kaplan-Meier analysis (**Figure S9**).

366

367 **Subgroup analyses and sensitivity analyses**

368 **Table S5** presents the associations between the metabolic signature and risk of
369 incident dementia, stratified by age, sex and *APOE* ϵ 4 carrier's status. Our
370 observations consistently indicate that the metabolic signature is associated with a
371 reduced risk of dementia and its subtypes across various strata, including age (<65
372 years or \geq 65 years), sex (female or male), and *APOE* ϵ 4 carrier status (yes or no)
373 groups. In the sensitivity analyses, the findings remained robust when excluding the
374 participants who developed incident dementia within three years of follow-up
375 duration (**Table S6**), restricting individuals aged > 60 y (**Table S7**), additional
376 adjustment for diabetes medication, antihypertensive medication, lipid-lowering
377 medication, and use of aspirin (**Table S8**), and conducting data interpolation (**Table**
378 **S9**).

379

380 **Mediation effects underlying metabolic signature-dementia association**

381 The increase of selected brain structure volumes, including GM, WM, total
382 hippocampus, GM in specific brain region, putamen, thalamus, caudate, and amygdala
383 were observed to be associated with reduced dementia risk (**Figure S10**). Further, we
384 found that the total metabolic signature and most of selected metabolite were
385 suggested to be significantly associated with the brain structure (**Figure S11 and**
386 **Figure S12**). The potential mediated roles of specific brain structure underlying
387 metabolic signature-dementia association were estimated and measured by mediated

388 proportion (%). As showed in **Table 3**, Gray matter, hippocampus, GM in the
389 hippocampus, GM in the parahippocampal gyrus, GM in the middle temporal gyrus,
390 and putamen were detected to account for the observed associations (Benjamini-
391 Hochberg P -value <0.05). Notably, GM in the hippocampus was found to have a
392 strong mediating effect, explaining 10.11% (95% CI: 4.12%, 16.11%). Similarly, we
393 also observed the strong mediation effects of the above-mentioned brain structures on
394 associations between specific metabolites, metabolic pathways, and all-cause
395 dementia (**Figure 3 and Figure S13**). For example, GM in the hippocampus and GM
396 in the parahippocampal gyrus could explain declined dementia risk attributed to
397 percentage of phospholipids to total lipids in large HDL.

398

399 **Mendelian randomization analyses**

400 The findings from mendelian randomization analyses show the concordant
401 associations with results from the observational study (**Figure 4, Figures S14 and**
402 **S15**). We observed that most of the genetically elevated levels of relative lipoprotein
403 lipid concentrations and lipoprotein subclasses were associated with the dementia risk.
404 For example, genetically elevated levels of cholesteryl esters, free cholesterol to total
405 lipids in small HDL percentage and large LDL percentage, and triglyceride, free
406 cholesterol, cholesteryl esters, and cholesterol to total lipids in very small VLDL
407 percentage were associated with a higher dementia risk. Furthermore, genetically
408 elevated levels of phospholipids to total lipids in small HDL percentage, small LDL
409 percentage, IDL percentage, large VLDL percentage, and extremely large VLDL
410 percentage were found to be linked a lower risk of dementia. The results from
411 sensitivity analyses yielded the similar estimates (**Tables S10-S12**).

412

413 **Discussion**

414 **Summary of the findings**

415 In current analysis using data from UK Biobank study, we identified and validated 83
416 metabolites, and subsequently established a metabolic signature in response to healthy

417 lifestyle. The metabolic signature was suggested to confer a reduced risk of incident
418 dementia (including ACD, AD, and VaD). Mendelian randomization analysis
419 indicated a causal association of the identified metabolites with dementia risk. In
420 addition, our findings revealed the potential biological mechanisms indicating that
421 preservation of specific brain structure (hippocampus, GM in the hippocampus, GM
422 in the parahippocampal gyrus and GM in the middle temporal gyrus) could explain the
423 observed associations.

424

425 **Comparison with previous literature**

426 Previous studies have established connections between metabolomics and healthy
427 lifestyle factors, shedding light on the intricate relationship between individual
428 metabolic processes and behaviors such as diet, physical activity, smoking, alcohol
429 consumption, and sleep³⁰⁻³⁵. In our own investigation, we identified a metabolic
430 signature comprising 83 metabolites that exhibited robust associations with a healthy
431 lifestyle across seven components, ultimately demonstrating a protective effect
432 against dementia. Our findings are consistent with similar research efforts that have
433 utilized metabolomic profiling as a reflection of a composite healthy lifestyle score to
434 explore associations with various health outcomes. For example, Fu and colleagues
435 identified healthy lifestyle-related metabolites, and observed a significant impact on
436 incident coronary artery disease¹⁴. An observational study of ~ 80000 participants
437 determined a metabolic signature comprising 81 metabolites to reflect healthy
438 lifestyle, suggesting a reduced risk of rheumatoid arthritis³⁶. However, no prior
439 research has endeavored to identify a metabolic signature capable of assessing
440 metabolic response to the multidomain lifestyle strategies, while concurrently
441 exploring its connection to the long-term risk of dementia. Some studies have directly
442 identified metabolic markers associated with dementia, which served as the
443 supplement for prediction and risk stratification of dementia^{37,38}. However, these
444 studies did not incorporate lifestyle factors or establish a distinct metabolic signature.
445 In addition, a targeted metabolomics study examined both brain and blood

446 metabolites, highlighting the significance of sphingolipid metabolism in the early
447 detection of Alzheimer's dementia ³⁹. Concordantly in our study, a substantial number
448 of lipid-related metabolites were identified, which might play a pivotal role in
449 neuronal function and integrity.

450

451 The identified metabolic signature indeed serves as a comprehensive reflection of the
452 overall metabolic homeostasis in response to multidomain lifestyle strategies.

453 Moreover, this metabolic profile also captures intricate interplay among genetic
454 susceptibility, the microbiome, and other individual-specific factors ^{10, 40}. In contrast,
455 when considering self-reported healthy lifestyle as an external exposure variable, it is
456 more likely to introduce measurement and reporting bias and not fully capture the
457 intricacies of how they affect the underlying metabolic processes. By leveraging the
458 metabolic signature, we gain a more objective and direct insight into the metabolic
459 changes associated with multidomain lifestyle interventions. This signature provides a
460 valuable tool for understanding how lifestyle choices impact an individual's metabolic
461 health, while also accounting for the metabolic variations resulting from other factors.

462

463 Prior studies have not fully elucidated the underlying physiological mechanism
464 between healthy lifestyle-related metabolites and dementia risk. Evidence from our
465 exploratory analyses have potentially shed light on the brain structural changes that
466 may explain the total effects of metabolic signature-dementia association.

467 Specifically, total hippocampus volume and GM volume within the hippocampus
468 were identified as the paramount mediators in the observed association, which aligns
469 with prior research findings ⁴¹⁻⁴³. The hippocampus is highly susceptible to dementia.

470 Changes in hippocampal volume, including reductions in total volume and GM
471 volume, are commonly observed in individuals with dementia. These structural
472 alterations in the hippocampus are strongly correlated with the cognitive deficits
473 commonly observed in dementia, particularly memory impairment ⁴⁴. Furthermore,
474 it's noteworthy that GM volume in regions such as the parahippocampal gyrus and

475 middle temporal gyrus also contribute to mediating this association to some extent.
476 These brain regions are intricately linked with the hippocampus and contribute to the
477 complex neural network responsible for memory and other cognitive processes ⁴⁵.
478 Brain structural changes, particularly within the hippocampus and related regions,
479 may serve as a key physiological bridge between healthy lifestyle-related metabolites
480 and the risk of developing dementia.

481

482 Our study has important implications for clinical and public health practice and
483 strategies. First, the identification of 83 metabolites related to a healthy lifestyle and
484 the establishment of a metabolic signature hold the potential to offer new biomarkers
485 or screening tools for assessing dementia risk. This could have promising clinical
486 applications for early intervention and personalized medicine. Additionally, our
487 findings underscore the importance of adopting a healthy lifestyle, as indicated by the
488 metabolic signature, in reducing the risk of dementia. This emphasizes the critical role
489 of lifestyle interventions in mitigating the overall burden of dementia at the
490 population level. Moreover, this study also provides insights into the biological
491 mechanisms connecting changes in brain structures, such as hippocampal volume and
492 gray matter in specific regions, to dementia risk. This knowledge can inform targeted
493 interventions designed to protect and promote brain health.

494

495 There are several limitations in our study. First, this study relied on data from the UK
496 Biobank and did not fully represent the broad, total population (eg, lack of
497 racial/ethnic diversity), which could limit the generalizability of our findings.

498 Validations across other populations are warranted. Second, due to the nature of the
499 observational study, it cannot establish causality. Third, self-reported data for lifestyle
500 factors can be subject to recall bias and reporting errors. Additionally, metabolite
501 measurements, while comprehensive, are not immune to measurement errors or
502 variability. Fourth, despite our efforts to control for various confounding factors, there
503 may still be unaccounted or residual confounding variables that could bias our results.

504 Fifth, while we have identified a metabolic signature associated with healthy lifestyles
505 and reduced dementia risk, the specific metabolic mechanisms underlying these
506 associations and the roles of brain structures require further investigation and
507 validation.

508

509 **Conclusion**

510 This study provides compelling evidence that a healthy lifestyle-associated metabolic
511 signature is inversely associated with dementia risk and that specific greater structural
512 brain reserve play an important mediating role. These findings have the potential to
513 inform targeted preventive strategies and personalized identification of at-risk
514 populations through metabolomics profiling, while also providing novel insights into
515 the brain structural mechanisms.

516

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523

524 **Competing interests**

525 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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527

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531

532 **Data availability**

533 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the UK Biobank
534 project site, subject to the registration and application process. Further details can be
535 found at <https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk>.

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- 640

641 **Table 1. Characteristics of study participants at baseline by dementia incidence**

Characteristics	Overall participants	Incident dementia	No incident dementia	<i>p</i> value *
No. of participants	136,628	1783	134845	
Age, years	56.14 (8.09)	64.10 (4.83)	56.03 (8.07)	<0.001
Sex, Female, n (%)	68527 (50.16)	726 (40.72)	67801 (50.28)	<0.001
Ethnicity, White, n (%)	131079 (95.94)	1728 (96.92)	129351 (95.93)	0.041
Townsend index	-1.57 (2.94)	-1.23 (3.12)	-1.58 (2.94)	<0.001
BMI	27.50 (4.65)	27.86 (4.74)	27.49 (4.65)	0.001
Higher education level, n (%)	66780 (49.09)	650 (36.97)	66130 (49.25)	<0.001
<i>APOE</i> ε4 carrier, n (%)	38872 (28.67)	922 (52.24)	37950 (28.36)	<0.001
Family history of dementia, n (%)	22778 (16.67)	447 (25.07)	22331 (16.56)	<0.001
Hypertension, n (%)	58711 (42.97)	1152 (64.61)	57559 (42.69)	<0.001
Depression, n (%)	7088 (5.19)	126 (7.07)	6962 (5.16)	<0.001
Healthy lifestyle factors				
No current smoking, n (%)	74538 (54.56)	815 (45.71)	73723 (54.67)	<0.001
Moderate alcohol consumption, n (%)	36533 (26.74)	342 (19.18)	36191 (26.84)	<0.001
Healthy diet, n (%)	112346 (82.23)	1503 (84.30)	110843 (82.20)	0.023
Regular physical activity, n (%)	111108 (81.32)	1432 (80.31)	109676 (81.33)	0.285
Adequate sleep duration, n (%)	94550 (69.20)	1135 (63.66)	93415 (69.28)	<0.001
Less sedentary behavior, n (%)	97906 (71.66)	990 (55.52)	96916 (71.87)	<0.001
Frequent social contact, n (%)	126312 (92.45)	1596 (89.51)	124716 (92.49)	<0.001

642 BMI, body mass index; *APOE*, apolipoprotein E643 **P* values were calculated by χ^2 test or *t* test, as appropriate.

644

Table 2. Associations between dementia risk and healthy lifestyle score and metabolic signature using UK biobank baseline and first repeated data

Outcome	Models	Healthy lifestyle score		Metabolic signature (Baseline)		Metabolic signature (First repeated)	
		HR (95% CI) *	<i>p</i> -value	HR (95% CI) †	<i>p</i> -value	HR (95% CI) †	<i>p</i> -value
All-cause dementia	Age- and sex-adjusted model	0.83 (0.80, 0.86)	1.06*10 ⁻²²	0.84 (0.80, 0.87)	2.42*10 ⁻¹⁶	0.76 (0.60, 0.97)	0.027
	Multivariable-adjusted model ‡	0.86 (0.83, 0.90)	2.28*10 ⁻¹³	0.87 (0.83, 0.91)	7.46*10 ⁻⁹	0.73 (0.56, 0.96)	0.023
	Multivariable-adjusted + mutual adjustment §	0.87 (0.84, 0.91)	4.73*10 ⁻¹¹	0.89 (0.85, 0.93)	3.33*10 ⁻⁶	0.75 (0.57, 0.98)	0.036
Alzheimer's dementia	Age- and sex-adjusted model	0.91 (0.86, 0.97)	2.76*10 ⁻³	0.91 (0.85, 0.98)	0.011	0.97 (0.66, 1.44)	0.882
	Multivariable-adjusted model ‡	0.96 (0.90, 1.02)	0.184	0.94 (0.87, 1.02)	0.161	0.86 (0.56, 1.32)	0.494
	Multivariable-adjusted + mutual adjustment §	0.96 (0.90, 1.03)	0.257	0.95 (0.88, 1.03)	0.226	0.87 (0.57, 1.34)	0.529
Vascular dementia	Age- and sex-adjusted model	0.74 (0.69, 0.80)	6.60*10 ⁻¹⁴	0.75 (0.70, 0.80)	1.62*10 ⁻¹⁸	0.59 (0.34, 1.04)	0.071
	Multivariable-adjusted model ‡	0.80 (0.73, 0.86)	4.38*10 ⁻⁸	0.82 (0.75, 0.88)	6.59*10 ⁻⁷	0.61 (0.31, 1.19)	0.147
	Multivariable-adjusted + mutual adjustment §	0.82 (0.75, 0.89)	9.08*10 ⁻⁷	0.84 (0.77, 0.91)	6.28*10 ⁻⁵	0.60 (0.31, 1.17)	0.134

HR, hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval, BMI, body mass index; *APOE*, apolipoprotein E.

*HR and 95% CI of dementia risk each point increase in healthy lifestyle scores.

†HR and 95% CI of dementia risk per standard deviation increase in metabolic signatures.

‡Adjustment for age, sex, ethnicity, Townsend index, education level BMI, family history, *APOE* ε4 carrier's status and prevalent status of hypertension, diabetes, and depression.

§Further including both lifestyle score and the metabolic signature simultaneously in the multivariable-adjusted model to assess their independent associations

Table 3. The proportion mediated by brain structure on the associations between metabolic signature and dementia risk

Brain structure	Proportion mediated (%)	Unadjusted <i>p</i>-value	Benjamini-Hochberg <i>p</i>-value
Total brain	0.81 (-1.21, 2.83)	0.301	0.477
Gray matter (GM)	3.96 (0.82, 7.09)	<0.001	0.025
White matter (WM)	0.01 (-1.82, 1.82)	0.988	0.988
Hippocampus	8.36 (3.74, 12.99)	<0.001	<0.001
GM in the hippocampus	10.11 (4.12, 16.11)	<0.001	<0.001
GM in the superior frontal gyrus	0.24 (-3.03, 3.51)	0.523	0.621
GM in the inferior frontal gyrus	2.45 (0.09, 4.81)	0.045	0.107
GM in the middle frontal gyrus	0.00 (-1.42, 1.43)	0.946	0.988
GM in frontal pole	1.96 (-0.23, 4.15)	0.081	0.150
GM in the precentral gyrus	1.38 (-3.47, 6.23)	0.465	0.621
GM in the postcentral gyrus	0.92 (-4.67, 6.51)	0.603	0.674
GM in the precuneus	1.94 (-1.95, 5.83)	0.443	0.621
GM in the parahippocampal gyrus	6.82 (2.96, 10.68)	<0.001	<0.001
GM in the middle temporal gyrus	4.09 (1.31, 6.88)	<0.001	<0.001
GM in the inferior temporal gyrus	1.56 (-0.16, 3.29)	0.087	0.150
Putamen	2.24 (0.16, 4.33)	<0.001	<0.001
Thalamus	1.23 (-2.28, 4.75)	0.503	0.621
Caudate	1.88 (-0.42, 4.18)	0.085	0.150
Amygdala	2.47 (0.20, 4.74)	0.041	0.107

Figure Legends

Figure 1. The metabolic signature for adherence to the healthy lifestyle: flowchart of study design and analytic approach. A, The training and testing procedures of a metabolic signature for the healthy lifestyle; B, Correlations between healthy lifestyle score and the metabolic signature using baseline data (training set); C, Correlations between healthy lifestyle score and the metabolic signature using first repeated data (testing set).

Figure 2. Associations between 83 metabolites constituting the metabolic signature and healthy lifestyle score, each healthy lifestyle component, and dementia risk. Presented from top to bottom are the metabolites' coefficients (weights) in the metabolic signature and associations with each healthy lifestyle components, healthy lifestyle score, and subsequent dementia risk. Coefficients for associations with healthy lifestyle score and each healthy lifestyle component indicate the SD changes in metabolites per healthy lifestyle component's score increment. Coefficients for the dementia risk indicate ln (HR) of dementia risk per SD increment in metabolites. Colors indicate the direction of association, with red representing positive associations and blue indicating inverse associations. The darkness of the color corresponds to the magnitude of the association. Asterisks denote the significance level of associations (* $p < 0.05$ and ** Bonferroni-corrected $p < 0.05$). C, cholesterol; CE, cholesteryl ester; FC, free cholesterol; M, medium; PL, phospholipid; TG, triglyceride; S, small; L, large; VLDL, very LDL; XL, very large; XS, very small; XXL, especially large.

Figure 3. The proportion mediated by brain structure on the associations of each selected metabolites with dementia risk. Colors indicate the magnitude of the mediated proportion, with red representing a higher proportion. GM, gray matter; C, cholesterol; CE, cholesteryl ester; FC, free cholesterol; M, medium; PL, phospholipid; TG, triglyceride; S, small; L, large; VLDL, very LDL; XL, very large; XS, very small;

XXL, especially large.

Figure 4. Mendelian randomization analyses of associations between genetically determined metabolite with all-cause dementia. Colors indicate the direction of association, with red representing positive associations and blue indicating inverse associations. Asterisks denote the significance level of associations (* $p < 0.05$ and ** Benjamini-Hochberg $p < 0.05$). C, cholesterol; CE, cholesteryl ester; FC, free cholesterol; M, medium; PL, phospholipid; TG, triglyceride; S, small; L, large; VLDL, very LDL; XL, very large; XS, very small; XXL, especially large.